

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and
assessment of plastic pollution

Short report on methods and protocols for the analysis of nano-, micro-, and macroplastic in biota

EUROqCHARM Short Report

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About EUROqCHARM

This report is part of a project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action programme under Grant Agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM).

Plastic pollution has become a global environmental and societal concern in recent years. Numerous protocols have been developed to monitor plastic litter globally, but these are rarely comparable. This has hindered gathering of knowledge regarding pollution sources, development of monitoring programmes and risk assessments, and implementation of mitigation measures. To develop long-term solutions to reduce plastic pollution, it is essential to establish harmonised methodologies. EUROqCHARM will address this by critically reviewing state-of-the-art analytical methods and, taking harmonisation one step further, validating them through an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) study. This will bring together prominent laboratories in environmental plastics analysis and will produce certified reference materials to be marketed for at least three of the four target matrices (water, soil/sediment, biota, air), during and after project completion.

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability and reliability. We will identify Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAP), resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP will be validated in terms of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) to decide if further validation is needed (by ILC).

Blueprints for standards, recommendations for policy and legislation and support for the establishment of acceptable reference levels and environmental targets will be given. This will include a roadmap for harmonised data collection and management, where policy analysis and coherence will be integral parts. To maximise impact, EUROqCHARM will also establish and consolidate an operational network for plastic monitoring, stimulating Transnational Joint Actions built on existing and future European and international initiatives.

The multi-stakeholder composition of EUROqCHARM puts the group in a unique position to achieve these ambitious goals.

More information on the project can be found at: www.EUROqCHARM.eu

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Executive Summary

A systematic review was carried out to assess currently available methods for plastic pollution research and monitoring in biota. Methodological steps from sampling to data management were arranged in Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs) and assessed for the Technological Readiness Level (TRL), which may eventually (if not already) be incorporated into plastic monitoring programmes.

For analysis of plastics in biota, the class size of the plastic particles is inherently linked to the biota group under investigation. In birds, research and monitoring is especially focused on particles larger than 1 mm, whereas for fish, bivalves and non-bivalve invertebrates, a lower cut-off size smaller than 0.1 mm is often reported. This also means that for birds, due to the larger plastic fragments, different analytical methods are in use compared to the three other groups.

The sampling of plastic in birds is mainly based on the work of Van Franeker (2011) and Provencher (2017, 2019) and is also used within OSPAR monitoring. Samples are collected by hand and plastic is determined in the gastrointestinal tract of dead birds. Particles are visually separated and analysed. For the other matrices, a wide range of sample collection methods is in use. Fish is often caught using active and passive (hooks/lines, pots/traps) fishing techniques whereas bivalves are mainly collected by hand, but they can also be collected as bycatch in trawls. In contrast to fish and bivalves, non-bivalve invertebrates are a diverse group including worms, crabs, and gastropods resulting in a large variety of sampling techniques. In the laboratory, a digestion step is needed to ensure the determination of small microplastics in biota. This is mainly done by using alkaline digestion with KOH while oxidative digestion with H₂O₂ is also frequently applied. A digestion step can be combined with density separation. Optical microscopy is the most frequently applied plastic identification technique. It allows aside from visual analysis the combination with polymer identification techniques such as FTIR, μ FTIR or μ Raman. Other techniques such as pyrolysis-GC-MS or fluorometric-based techniques are only used in a few cases on real environmental samples. The majority of the publications do not provide detailed information on air blanks, procedure blanks or positive controls.

The highest TRL is observed for birds. Existing protocols are in place, which provide information on the minimum size of the plastic to consider, the sample preparation and analysis steps to apply and the procedure for plastic registration. The procedure is based on visual separation and visual analysis and is considered to reach a TRL of 8 or 9. For the other sub-compartments, there is no single commonly applied protocol in use, although multiple methods are well developed and applied, resulting in a TRL of at least 6. Finally, overall better quality control is required by consequently introducing procedure blanks, air blanks and positive controls when smaller plastic fragments are analysed.

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This report was compiled by members of WP1 who contributed to different degrees across the whole work package. Specifically, Bavo De Witte, Katrien Verlé, Michael Dekimpe, David Vanavermaete (ILVO), Amy Lusher, Emilie Kallenbach (NIVA), Jakob Strand (AU), Esteban Holgado, Marinella Farré Urgell (CSIC).

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List of acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
GIT	Gastro-Intestinal Tract
OSPAR	Oslo-Paris Convention
RAPs	Reproducible Analytical Pipelines
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Acronym	Full name
NIVA	Norsk institutt for vannforskning <i>Norwegian Institute for Water Research</i>
ILVO	Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek <i>Flemish Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research</i>
AU	Aarhus University
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas <i>Spanish Research Council</i>

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large-scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability, and reliability. The main goal of the first EUROqCHARM Work Package (WP1) was to define matrix- and size- adapted methods which may eventually be incorporated into plastic monitoring programmes. To do so, WP1 used a systematic approach to assess methods employed by the international research community and identify state-of-the art procedures for sample collection, sample preparation and analysis of plastics from environmental samples to define matrix- and size- adapted method. **Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs)** could be extracted for each element in the analytical chain, resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP was further validated in terms of **Technological Readiness Level (TRL)** to decide if further validation is needed.

The workload was thereby divided across four tasks addressing plastics in different size ranges (nano-, micro-, macroplastics) in different matrices (water, soil/sediment, air, biota). The specific objectives of WP1 were to:

- Identify existing methods - including the level of currently applied QA/QC procedures for the quantification of nano-, micro-, and macro-plastics in different matrices.
- Evaluate the identified methods for their suitability to be incorporated into monitoring programmes including their advantages and limitations. The most promising methods were suggested for validation and quality control in WP2 or direct implementation into WP3.

Therefore, the **key outputs** of WP1 were to compile existing methods and protocols used to quantify plastics in environmental matrices (using RAPs), evaluate them for further validation (WP2) or direct implementation in monitoring programmes (WP3);

The main actions in WP1 were:

- Systematic literature review;
- Synthesis of existing methods and procedures;
- Compilation of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs);
- Analyses of methods Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT);
- Suggestions for critical revisions of identified monitoring methods.

All these objectives and tasks were attempted for plastic of sizes ranging from macro- to nanoplastics in water, sediment, biota and air, with both marine and terrestrial environments.

In the present report, **the RAPs from plastics in biota are shortly presented.**

2. Methods

For the matrix biota, a systematic review was performed by EUROqCHARM partners ILVO, AU, NIVA and CSIC. Selection of plastic size class and species are inherently linked for this matrix, as will be described in the section on survey design. A total of 408 papers was retrieved. A detailed analysis was performed for each step of the analytical procedure providing the number of entries was more than 10, indicating a TRL of 3 to 5. Percentages reported in this chapter are always calculated after omitting the non-relevant entries such as not applicable or not reported. Further details on the method can be found in Aliani et al. (2023).

3. Results

3.1. RAPs for plastics in biota

3.1.1. Survey design for plastic analysis in biota (all sub-compartments)

The number of publications from environmental studies on plastics in biota has strongly increased over the last decade. Most research papers focused on the analysis of plastics in fish (173 publications), followed by non-bivalve invertebrates (87 publications), bivalves (60 publications) and birds (59 publications). Research on mammals, reptiles, plants or other species was too limited to deduce Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs).

The selection of the sub-compartment was region dependent. In Europe, Asia and South America, fish was the most selected biota matrix. In North America and Oceania, relatively more research has been performed on plastics in seabirds (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Number of publications on plastics in birds, bivalves, fish and non-bivalve invertebrates per continent.

The choice of which sub-compartment to consider is clearly linked to the plastic size range that is investigated. Filter feeders such as bivalves can only ingest small microplastics (Beecham 2008), resulting in a majority of publications on bivalves with a cut off size limit below 0.1 mm. Protocols on plastic in birds mainly focus on larger plastics, often starting at a minimum size of 1 mm or larger (e.g., Van Franeker et al. 2011, Provencher et al. 2019). For fish, a more equal spread can be found with reported cut off sizes varying from <0.1 mm to 0.1-0.3 mm, 0.3 mm - 1 mm and 1-5 mm. Research publications on environmental nanoplastics in biota stay very limited for all compartments,

with only two publications on nanoparticles retained by the systematic review process (Correia et al. 2018, White et al. 2018).

3.1.2. RAPs for plastic analysis in fish

RAPs for plastic analysis in fish are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Overview of RAPs for microplastics in fish. The different digestion types are summarised for “digestion only” and “digestion and density” and are illustrated with black and grey arrows, respectively. Techniques with less than 10 occurrences are not reported and labelled as other. For visibility reasons, data quantification, quality control and data reporting is not included in this figure, but discussed in text.

Sample collection

A wide range of sample collection methods has been applied in fish studies. The most encountered fishing gear was a trawl, but passive gear and fishing activities employing hooks and lines are also used, as well as various seine fishing methods. Within 87% of the retrieved publications for fish, analyses were performed on the gastro-intestinal tract (GIT) and/or stomach. The sample size is mainly expressed as a “number of individuals”.

Sample preparation

Analysis of plastics in fish mostly involves multiple sample preparation steps. A digestion step is included in the majority of the methods, although visual separation without digestion is also frequently applied (Figure 3). Plastics are mostly extracted and separated using alkaline digestion with KOH (Figure 4). In 16% of the methods, a digestion step is combined with a density separation step. NaCl is the most applied salt.

Figure 3 – Sample preparation procedure for different biota matrices.

Figure 4 – Digestion type for plastic analysis in biota.

Analytical detection

Optical microscopy is the most frequently applied plastic identification technique (Figure 5). This technique is mostly combined with a polymer confirmation technique such as FTIR, μ FTIR or μ Raman (Figure 5). The use of methods based on pyrolysis-GC-MS, fluorometry or hyperspectral imaging on fish samples stays limited with at maximum 2 retrieved papers for each of these methods (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Applied analytical techniques for plastic detection in different biota matrices.

Figure 6 – Reporting units for plastics in biota.

Plastic quantification and quality control

For fish, the majority of the publications report plastic items per individual. As analysis is frequently done on one individual, the % of positive samples is frequently provided (Figure 6). 12% of the publications report as items per mass, often in combination with other metrics.

Regarding quality control, 38% of publications included air blanks and 40% of publications included procedure blanks. Positive control samples were only applied in 12% of the publications.

Data reporting

There is no general use of a common data reporting protocol and data is generally not reported in national or international databases at the date of publication. Raw data is mostly not shared, or publications do not report on the accessibility status of the data.

3.1.3. RAPs for plastic analysis in bivalves

RAPs for plastic analysis in bivalves are illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – Overview of RAPs for microplastics in bivalves. The different digestion types are summarised for “digestion only” and “digestion and density” and are illustrated with black and grey arrows, respectively. Techniques with less than 10 occurrences are not reported and labelled as other. For visibility reasons, data quantification, quality control and data reporting is not included in this figure, but discussed in text.

Sample collection

Bivalves are mainly hand-collected. 59% of the publications define “number of individuals” as sample size, whereas 39% of the retrieved papers specify a weight range.

Sample preparation

For the bivalve sub-compartment, matrix is mostly digested using alkaline digestion with KOH or oxidative digestion with H₂O₂ (Figure 7). In 28% of the cases, this is combined with a density separation using NaCl or NaI.

Analytical detection

Microplastics in bivalves are mainly identified with optical microscopy in combination with polymer identification such as FTIR and μFTIR, while only 36% of the methods apply optical microscopy only or in combination with a melting point technique (Figure 5).

Plastic quantification and quality control

For bivalves, multiple reporting units are mostly combined, with 58% of publications reporting a number of items per individual and 68% reporting items per mass (Figure 6). Most publication make use of procedure blanks but the use of air blanks and positive controls samples is less common.

Data reporting

There is no general use of a common data reporting protocol and data is generally not reported in national or international databases at the date of publication. Raw data is mostly not shared, or publications do not report on the accessibility status of the data.

3.1.4. RAPs for plastic analysis in birds

Figure 8 presents RAPs for plastic analysis in birds.

Figure 8 – Overview of RAPs for microplastics in birds. Techniques with less than 10 occurrences are not reported and labelled as other. For visibility reasons, data quantification, quality control and data reporting is not included in this figure, but discussed in text.

Sample collection

For plastic analysis in birds, dead birds are mainly collected by hand (e.g., van Franeker et al. 2011). In 81% of the publications, analysis are done within the gastro-intestinal tract (GIT) and/or stomach. The sample size is mostly determined as a number of individuals.

Sample preparation

The analysis of plastics in birds often involves only one sample preparation step, mostly a visual separation of plastics (Figure 3).

Analytical detection

For plastic analysis in birds, 42% of the publications apply a visual inspection. Due to the focus on larger particles, most methods on plastics do not identify the polymer composition (Figure 5).

Plastic quantification and quality control

Most publication on plastics in bird report a number of items per individual or a total amount of plastics in g per individual (Figure 6). Since identification of plastics in birds is focused on particles larger than 1 mm, quality assessments such as air blanks, procedural blanks, positive controls, and the use of air filtration systems are often absent, not reported, or not applicable.

Data reporting

Data recording for birds is mainly based on the work of Van Franeker (2011) and Provencher (2017, 2019) and is also used by OSPAR for the registration of plastics in birds. However, data is generally not reported in national or international databases at the date of publication. Raw data is mostly not shared, or publications do not report on the accessibility status of the data.

3.1.5. RAPs for plastic analysis in non-bivalve invertebrates

Figure 9 presents RAPs for plastic analysis in non-bivalve invertebrates.

Figure 9 – Overview of RAPs for microplastics in non-bivalve invertebrates. The different digestion types are summarised for “digestion only” and “digestion and density” and are illustrated with black and grey arrows, respectively. Techniques with less than 10 occurrences are not reported and labelled as other. For visibility reasons, data quantification, quality control and data reporting is not included in this figure, but discussed in text.

Sample collection

As this is a diverse group (including worms, crabs, gastropods, etc.), a large variety of sampling techniques has been applied, from hand-collecting to using trawls, nets, bongos, etc.

Sample preparation

Plastics in invertebrates are mainly extracted using alkaline digestion with KOH, acid digestion with HNO₃, or oxidative digestion with H₂O₂. In 13% of the cases, digestion is combined with a density separation using NaCl or NaI.

Analytical detection

Plastics are mainly identified applying optical microscopy in combination with polymer identification. Seven papers retrieved by the systematic review also applied fluorometric based techniques for microplastic determination.

Plastic quantification and quality control

Data on plastics in invertebrates is most often reported as items per individual, items per g or items per g tissue (Figure 6). A procedural blank is used in 54% of the cases. However, other quality assessments such as air blanks, positive controls, or the use of an air filtration system are often not used, not reported, or not applicable.

Data reporting

There is no general use of a common data reporting protocol and data is generally not reported in national or international databases at the date of publication. Raw data is mostly not shared, or publications do not report on the accessibility status of the data.

3.2. TRL evaluation

Table 1. Summary table of TRLs for plastic (>1 mm) analysis in biota

TRL	Survey design	Sample collection	Sample preparation	Analytical detection	Plastic quantification	QA/QC	Data reporting
1							
2							
3							
4							
5	Mammals						
6	Fish, Reptiles			Chemical ID with FTIR (ATR, general and microscopy)			
7			Alkaline digestion, oxidative digestion				Research protocols
8							
9	Birds	Hand collection, nets, hooks/lines	Visual separation	Visual	Guidelines for shapes and colour Items/individual, g/individual, %		International protocols (e.g., OSPAR)

Table 2. Summary table of TRLs for microplastic (<1 mm) analysis in biota

TRL	Survey design	Sample collection	Sample preparation	Analytical detection	Plastic quantification	QA/QC	Data reporting
1							
2							
3							
4				Hyperspectral imaging			
5	Plants, amphibian			Pyr-GC/MS Fluorometric		Field blanks, Positive controls	
6	Non-bivalve invertebrates		Enzymatic digestion, acid digestion		µg/g	Air blanks	
7	Bivalves, fish		Alkaline digestion, oxidative digestion, density separation	Optical microscopy, FTIR, µFTIR, Raman, µRaman	Items/individual, items/g, %	Air filtrations systems	
8						Procedure blanks	
9		Hand collection, nets, hooks/lines					

Table 3. Summary table of TRLs for nanoplastic analysis in biota

TRL	Survey design	Sample collection	Sample preparation	Analytical detection	Plastic quantification	QA/QC	Data reporting
1	All biota subcompartments				Method development	Method development	Method development
2							
3			Enzymatic digestion, alkaline digestion,				
4				Atomic force microscopy, field flow fractionation - multi-angle light scattering			
5							
6							
7							
8							
9		Hand collection, nets, hooks/lines					

4. Discussion

For plastic analysis in biota, sufficient publications to construct RAPs were retrieved for the sub-compartments fish, bivalves, birds and non-bivalve invertebrates. Selection of plastic size class and species are inherently linked, with a higher lower-size limit for methods on plastics in birds, often 1 mm or higher, while methods on plastics in fish, bivalves and non-bivalve invertebrates mostly have a lower size limit below 0.3 mm or even below 0.1 mm. Determination of nanoplastics in biota is currently still at the stage of basic research, with TRL below 3.

Within the compartment biota, RAPs for plastic determination in birds reach the highest TRL. Existing protocols are in place, which provide information on the minimum size of the plastic to consider, the

sample preparation, analysis steps to apply and the procedure for plastic registration. The procedure is based on visual separation and visual analysis, and is considered to reach a TRL of 8 or 9.

For the other sub-compartments, there is no single commonly applied protocol in use, although multiple RAPs are well developed and applied, resulting in a TRL of at least 6. Sample collection for fish, bivalves and non-bivalve invertebrates is mostly done by using trawls, other nets or by hand collecting biota. To analyse (micro)plastics in these sub-compartments, efficient matrix digestion is indispensable which is commonly done with an alkaline digestion with KOH or oxidative digestion with H₂O₂. This is often combined with a density separation using NaCl. For analytical detection, visual identification, the use of microscopy only or in combination with μ FTIR, FTIR and μ Raman are well documented. The use of methods based on pyrolysis-GC-MS, fluorometry or hyperspectral imaging stays limited, indicating that these techniques are currently not at the stage to be applied for routine analysis of plastics in complex matrices such as biota. However, method developments are still ongoing.

5. Conclusions

Existing monitoring methods dedicated to the quantification of plastics in biota have been identified, based on a systematic literature review. RAPs were constructed, and the Technological Readiness Level of each step of the RAP was assessed.

For matrix biota, the major conclusions deduced from the systematic review process were:

1. Research studies on plastics in biota are not equally distributed. Within Europe, many publications focused on the OSPAR region and the Mediterranean whereas no publications were found within the systematic review for the Black Sea region.
2. For the analysis of plastics in biota, RAPs could be constructed for plastics in fish, bivalves, birds and non-bivalve invertebrates. From these matrices, methods for plastics determination in birds reached the highest degree of standardisation with commonly used protocols available.
3. There is a clear link between the selected target species and the corresponding plastic size range investigated.
4. Visual determination or optical microscopy with polymer detection are methods of choice whereas the use of pyr-GC-MS, hyperspectral imaging or fluorometry is currently still limited.
5. Publications on nanoplastics in biota are limited.
6. The QA/QC is weakly described in many papers. The applied air filtration system is seldomly mentioned and positive control samples are often not applied.
7. Only a small part of the publications identified through the systematic review make their full dataset publicly available within the supplementary information or within Open Access data repositories.
8. Too many papers are lacking detailed information on contamination and no information is provided to assess if background contamination originates from the environment or just fieldwork, procedural or lab contamination.
9. Many papers do not report the lower size limit of particles that can be detected by the method.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. Monitoring studies on plastics in biota should select species based on the targeted particle size as well as other characteristics such as geographical distribution, ecological niche and conservation status.
2. There is a requirement for better quality control by systematically introducing procedural blanks, air blanks and positive controls when smaller plastic fragments are analysed. Development of a set of minimum QA/QC requirements and guidelines on how to apply these is recommended.
3. The lower size limit is an important characteristic of each method, essential for data comparability. It should always be reported. It can depend on the shape of the particle (fibre versus particle).
4. It is necessary to study how data from different continents can be harmonised or compared.
5. Because methods for nanoplastics determination in biota are currently not developed enough, more research is needed before implementation in monitoring programs.
6. Monitoring guidelines should provide data handling information, including the reporting of processed data (e.g. reporting of mean or median, using arithmetic or logarithmic mean), including details in methods description.

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